

Thucydidean Physical Philosophy of the Sicilian Expedition

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Abstract

Thucydides, whilst monumentally narrating the Peloponnesian War (431 – 404 B.C.), induces to his reader elements of Physical Philosophy by virtue of the connotations of historiographical, argumentative, Speech-delivering, and characterological points of his Opus. This is traced by the present Study in relation to his account (*History of the Peloponnesian War*, Book VII) of the Sicilian Expedition (414 – 413 B.C.), and it is herewith discussed in particular in conjunction with the Combat of Epipolae (Chapters 42 – 59) and the consequent final Naval Battle of Syracuse (Chapters 60 – 71): Field Marshal Nicias the Athenian emerges as the Protagonist of Action in these investigated Cases of Thucydidean interweaving of Historiography and Physical Philosophy.

Keywords:

Thucydides, Physical Philosophy, History of the Peloponnesian War, Sicilian Expedition.

1. Introduction

Owing to his soundly documented and carefully detailed narration of the Peloponnesian War (431 – 404 B.C.), to his scientifically causal interpretations of its commencement and evolution, to his eternally convincing and analogously applicable strategic, anthropological and philosophical comments, criteria and inherent advices, and equally owing to his enthusiastically wise and touchingly artistic richness of Syntax, Vocabulary and overall Style of Language, the indisputably unsurpassable Historiographer Thucydides the Halimousian, son of Olorus, (455 – 399 B.C. or 460 – 400 B.C.) has been being inexhaustibly studied and investigated through the centuries by Researchers of a multitude of official specialisations and interests of Knowledge Quest.

Characteristically, investigations of the brilliantly profound and marvelously beautiful Thucydidean Opus have been performed in the topical fields of the Philosophy of History [1], of the Philosophy of Individuality [2], of the Political Philosophy and of the Philosophy of International Relations [3], of the Strategic Crisis-Management [4], and even more thoroughly of the Science of War [5].

And yet, with respect to whether a functionality of Physical Philosophy is traceable in the Historiographic Essay of Thucydides, and therefore, as well, in his mentality and Conscience, it appears bibliographically that a less frequent focused research has been conducted: It has been mainly noted [6, 7] that, as regards experiencing the dipole “Nature – Law”, the general Philosophy permeating his Work reflects elements of the Sophistical Movement (which had become operative in Athens around the middle of the 5th Century B.C.). That is to say, of a Movement proceeding in opposition to the already established Currents of pure Physical Philosophy of Thales, Anaximander and Anaximenes of the School of Miletus (6th Century B.C.), of the (also Physical as alternatively “Cosmological”) Pythagorean Doctrines (cultivated at Croton of Lower Italy since 530 B.C.) concerning a Universal Harmony based on Arithmetic Analogies, and of the Quest of Physical Laws governing the Evolution of Species and Repetitive Transformation of Energy (served by Heraclitus, Parmenides, Empedocles, Anaxagoras of the Second Generation of Greek Philosophers). Of a Movement, furthermore, being in Ontological discord to the (highly Physical) Atomic Theory of Matter conceived by Leucippus of Miletus and Democritus of Abdera and ultimately (since the early 20th Century A.C.) justified as the notional generator of Elementary-Particle Physics.

Evidently, in parallel to Philosophy, Dramatic Poetry, Sculpture, Painting, Architecture and, even more admirably, Oratory applied to Forensic and Political Speech (especially in regard to Political Persuasion on War and Peace) are thriving in the Athenian Democracy of the Golden Age of Pericles: All these cultural facets are, of course, inducing a broad spectrum of argumentative private and public assessment (of praise and, at times, of expenditure criticism) suggesting to the fervent Family Friend of Pericles, Thucydides, the need and value of a (Sophistic) Scepticism questioning the “Absolute Truth” dwelling within a Theatrical Drama and a material Artifact or declaimed in Court about guilt or innocence and on the Areopagus for a (Legislative) Decision of the Ecclesia of the Demus (General Assembly of the Voting Citizens). Expectedly, Thucydides is sensing that Sophistic Discourse is inevitably partaking of the ignition, the planning and the execution of War Clashes.

And yet, the veracity, bravery and piety of Conscience of Thucydides cannot be impeded by trends promoting or accommodating ambiguity: He composes a personal Values Hierarchy conducive to the altruistic Public Service of scientific compilation and enlightening deciphering of the greatest intro-Hellenic ancient War. This pious mentality of his may, as the present Study comes to believe, be accompanied by an earnest readiness to feel, consider and acknowledge the Mystic Marvelousness of Nature and, therefore, by an alertness to observe and perceive the Physical Phenomena coupled with a desire or spontaneity to include psychic impacts of (impressive) Physical Phenomena in the set of Interpretation Factors pertaining, among others, to selecting and reviewing War Strategies.

2. Investigation of Two Excerpts from Book VII of the Thucydidean *HISTORY OF THE PELOPONNESIAN WAR*

In the current publication of this Study the investigation of two Excerpts from the Seventh Book of the Thucydidean narration of the Peloponnesian War, the Book referring to the critical phase of the Sicilian Expedition (the phases of the armed conflict of which have spanned mainly the Summer 414 – Summer 413 B.C. period) is registered in short; the first Excerpt is linked to the Combat of Epipolae and the second to the then ultimate Naval Battle of Syracuse:

2.a ἡ σελήνη ἐκλείπει πασσέληνος οὐσα

{Full-Moon Eclipse}

[«καὶ μελλόντων αὐτῶν, ἐπειδὴ ἐτοῖμα ἦν, ἀποπλεῖν ἡ σελήνη ἐκλείπει· ἐτύγχανε γὰρ πασσέληνος οὐσα. καὶ οἱ Ἀθηναῖοι οἳ τε πλείους ἐπισχεῖν ἐκέλευον τοὺς στρατηγούς ἐνθύμιον ποιούμενοι, καὶ ὁ Νικίας (ἦν γὰρ τι καὶ ἄγαν θειασμῶ τε καὶ τῶ τοιούτῳ προσκειμένος) οὐδ' ἂν διαβουλεύσασθαι ἔτι ἔφη πρὶν, ὡς οἱ μάντις ἐξηγοῦντο, τρις ἑννέα ἡμέρας μείναι, ὅπως ἂν πρότερον κινήθῃ. καὶ τοῖς μὲν Ἀθηναίοις μελλήσασι διὰ τοῦτο ἡ μονὴ ἐγεγένητο.»

(ΘΟΥΚΥΔΙΔΟΥ ΙΣΤΟΡΙΩΝ Ζ', 50.4)

{ "But after all was ready and when they were about to make their departure, the moon, which happened then to be at the full, was eclipsed. And most of the Athenians, taking the incident to heart, urged the Generals to wait. Nicias also, who was somewhat too much given to divination and the like, refused even to discuss further the question of their removal until they should have waited thrice nine days, as the soothsayers prescribed. Such, then, was the reason why the Athenians delayed and stayed on."

(Harvard University Press Loeb Classical Library English Translation of the

HISTORY OF THE PELOPONNESIAN WAR By THUCYDIDES,

Book VII, Chapt. 50, Par. 4) }] [8]

The augurial (as recognised by the ground-breaking Hellenic National Leader Eleutherius Venizelos (1864 – 1936 A.C) in his righteously famous Modern-Greek Translation of the Thucydidean Opus) perception by Nicias of the Eclipse of the Full Moon at a crucial instance (27th August 413 B.C.), in the aftermath of the Combat of Epipolae during the final phase of the Sicilian Expedition, and equally -if not more importantly- its connotation by Thucydides in this Passage is considered by the present Study as conveying an intellectual current of Physical Philosophy by virtue both of Existential Spontaneity and of Multidisciplinary Susceptibility:

On the one hand, by virtue of Existential Spontaneity in so far as a prime intertemporal functionality of a Man of sufficiently non-inert Conscience is his pious alertness to seek out any potential Supramundane Message encoded in an observable specific Synchronicity of a spectacular Physical Phenomenon with a critical turning-point of any serious personal or collective Endeavour or Struggle: A (Self-) Questioning immediately

emanating from such a Synchronicity may at times be hearing for a Supernal encouragement or warning with respect to the completion or interruption of a demanding Course of Action. Evidently then, an Augury (attempted soberly and modestly by the Intellect and the Psyche) thus tracing any (literal or metaphorical, according to the freedom of Personality of the Seeker) Devine Sign has nothing to do with either Superstition or Fatalism.

On the other hand, (an intellectual current of Physical Philosophy is conveyed) by virtue of Multidisciplinary Susceptibility in so far as the (preceding any Ontological) Observational Monitoring of the spectacular Physical Phenomenon and its Comparative Evaluation on the basis of personal Memory and Hearings of Experience of elders require, externalise and document a Scientific Mentality functioning lustingly after continually acquiring further Knowledge and accordingly showing a voluntary impetus of fertilising several fields of (personal) Scientific Thought towards consecutively all the more clearly comprehending the Cosmos and the Human Mission in it.

Whilst such invincibly eager and inspiringly exhilarating efforts are being made by the interested Mind and Conscience (in this case, of Nicias and the Historiographer inextricably) for a Meaningful Perception of astounding Physical Phenomena synchronous with Dramatic Phases of Life, a genetically ever-flourishing and inescapable kind of characteristically Milesian Physical Philosophy is indeed being exercised. But, at the same time (by means of gentleness and thoroughness of Thought and conscientious Ethos of the Thinker) a kind of Philosophy incorporating indices of Elements somehow insightful both of the Platonic Cosmology of Ideas (which would be being taught by the Founder at the Academia from 390 to 347 B.C.) and of the Aristotelian unhampered Synergy (which would be being achieved by the Stageirites from 347 to 323 B.C.) of Aretology (characteristically of the *Nicomachean Ethics*) and Physiognostico-Logical Positivism. Overall, this Study ventures to come to believe, a multi-component Thucydidean type of profound (as humanly spontaneous and interdisciplinarily researchful) integrated Philosophy, lustling after acquiring further Knowledge, could be plausibly identified.

The Historic-Time Moment focused upon by the considered Excerpt (and its conjugate Physio-Existential Event) being taken into account, the Thucydidean Physical Philosophy traced presents itself interlinked with a multi-parametric Strategy, the Athenian Strategy in the aftermath of the

Combat of Epipolae during the period of the Sicilian Expedition in the range of the Peloponnesian War: The outpouring, thus, reservations of Nicias resonate, as emanating from (subconscious) Physical Philosophy, with the anaclastic demand of the majority of the Athenian Force. It is worth mentioning, at this point, that according to the dominant Historical Attitude the ultimate (miserable) defeat of the Athenian Part is attributed to a later (impious with respect to the overall Enterprise and irrational with respect to the Science of War) surrendering of the arms of one Athenian-Force Corps, led by General Demosthenes having been deceitfully misled by the Spartan Field-Marshal Gylippus, and not to the (philosophically) sober rescheduling having prior to it been decided by Nicias for the sailing-away.

2.b *ἤρρηται δ' ἡμῖν ὅσα χρή ἀντιναυπηγήσαι*

{And we have contrived whatever counter-devices were necessary in the construction of our ships}

[*» ἤρρηται δ' ἡμῖν ὅσα χρή ἀντιναυπηγήσαι, καὶ πρὸς τὰς τῶν ἐπωτίδων αὐτοῖς παχύτητας, ὥπερ δὴ μάλιστα ἐβλαπτόμεθα, χειρῶν σιδηρῶν ἐπιβολαί, αἱ σχήσουσι τὴν πάλιν ἀνάκρουσιν τῆς προσπεσούσης νεώς, ἣν τὰ ἐπὶ τούτοις οἱ ἐπιβάται ὑπουργῶσιν. ἐς τοῦτο γὰρ δὴ ἠναγκάσμεθα ὥστε πεζομαχεῖν ἀπὸ τῶν νεῶν, καὶ τὸ μήτε αὐτοὺς ἀνακρούεσθαι μήτ' ἐκείνους ἐὰν ὠφέλιμον φαίνεται, ἄλλως τε καὶ τῆς γῆς, πλὴν ὅσον ἂν ὁ πεζὸς ἡμῶν ἐπέχη, πολεμίας οὔσης.*

ὧν χρή μεμνημένους διαμάχεσθαι ὅσον ἂν δύνηθε καὶ μὴ ἐξωθεῖσθαι ἐς αὐτήν, ... »

(*ΙΣΤΟΡΙΩΝ Ζ', 62.3 – 63.1*)

{ "And we have contrived whatever counter-devices were necessary in the construction of our ships, and especially to combat the thickness of the enemy's catheads, a device from which we suffered most injury, we have provided grappling-irons, which will prevent any ship that will have rammed us from backing off again, if the Marines perform the service that will then devolve upon them. For we have been forced to the extremity of having to fight a land-battle on shipboard, and it is manifestly to our interest neither to back water ourselves nor to suffer them to do so, especially since the whole shore, except the small part of it that our Force holds, is hostile.

Remembering these things, you must fight to the last with all your strength and not allow yourselves to be driven ashore , ..." }

(Harvard University Press *Loeb Classical Library* English Translation of the

HISTORY OF THE PELOPONNESIAN WAR By THUCYDIDES,

Book VII, Chapt. 62, Par. 3 – Chapt. 63, Par. 1) }] [8]

After the Combat of Epipolae and in view of the ultimate Naval Battle which would be fought against Syracuse (supported by a Spartan Army), during the phase of the Sicilian Expedition of the Peloponnesian War, Field Marshal Nicias the Athenian, in delivering his Commands Discourse to his assembled Allied Force, is encouraging them raising Arguments drawn from Physics applied to the Science of War. Since, at that, Thucydides is veraciously stating already in the first of the eight Books of his *HISTORIAE* that, whenever a Speech appears in his Opus, it is recorded with an Informational Content and in a Language Style carefully respecting (within the framework of his own earnest and analytic comprehension and reasoning) details of personal hearings and trustworthy testimonies of others, the present Study puts forward an Interpretation which attributes the Physical Philosophy conjugate to the above Arguments of Physics of War simultaneously to the Orator and the Historiographer, a dual Semantics of a Thucydidean Physical Philosophy thus possibly becoming meaningful.

The major component, now, of what Nicias is meaning by *ἀντιναυπήγησις τῶν νεῶν* { *application of counter-devices necessary for the Athenian Triremes to be capable of potentially neutralising the dangerous effectivity of reconfigurations unexpectedly incorporated in the Hostile Ships just before the previous Naval Battle* } had been the engineering of what is being named *χειρῶν σιδηρῶν ἐπιβολαί* { *provision of iron grapplers to be controlled by the Deck Marines of Athenian Triremes, whenever a Hostile Ship, already reinforced with frontal thick “catheads” (appropriate symmetrical collisional projections), would attack, so that it could adequately possibly be prevented from backing off* }. Highly worth mentioning, as the tracing and Interpretation of Thucydidean Physical Philosophy ventured by the present Study sees it, comes to be that the Historiographer feels the need to express this crucial strategic piece of information in the Syntax of the Conditional Speech of (hopeful) Expectation *χειρῶν σιδηρῶν ἐπιβολαί σχήσουσι τὴν πάλιν ἀνάκρουσιν τῆς νεώς, ἢν τὰ ἐπὶ τούτοις οἱ ἐπιβάται ὑπουργῶσιν* { *grappling-irons will prevent any ship that will have rammed us from backing off again, if the Marines perform the service that will then devolve upon them* } , in which the expected beneficial outcome of the

Athenian counter-device (the Outcome of the “Algorithm of Impeding the Backing-Off of the Hostile Ship) is being expected under the “Resonance Hypothesis” stated by the Conditional Clause (second part of the Conditional Speech, here).

It is with enthusiasm, therefore, that the Interpretation applied by the present Study is observing a Thucydidean Physical Philosophy of high-quality functionality permeating the scientific mental vision (both of the Athenian Field-Marshal and of the Historiographer) sensing procedures of Physical Phenomena which might or do influence parametrically pre-examined and planned Phases of the Ultimate Naval Battle of Syracuse.

The functionality, then, of the Thucydidean Physical Philosophy is found harmonising with the Physics of causal interrelation of the Dynamics of Desired and Expected Evolutions and Outcomes with Ergonomic Prerequisites (“Input Signals”), as well as of the synopsis of realistic Initial and Boundary Conditions with the Algorithm of Fighting the Naval Battle (the “Dynamic Equation”). And chiefly, the Interpretation put forward finds the functionality of the (intimately respecting and in effect “applying” Physics Criteria) overall evaluative and expressive Historiographical Style (therefore, through the prism of Conscience isomorphisms, of the integrated Ethos) recognisable both through the informational and argument-providing content of the Commands Speech of Nicias and through the Thucydidean recording picture of the Discourse.

3. Conclusion

Through investigating representative Passages of the (pertaining to the Sicilian Expedition) Book VII of the Thucydidean *History of the Peloponnesian War*, this Study traces a co-functioning of the historiographic grandeur with idiosyncratic both assimilation of elements of the Physical Philosophy of the School of Miletus and insightful approximation of parts of the Platonic Cosmology of Ideas and the Aristotelian Synergy of Aretology and Physiognostico – Logical Positivism. Such a dynamically stable and operationally robust superpositional Thucydidean Physical Philosophy is found adequately deducible from both Passages presented and analysed: The one concerning that during the Athenian preparation for sailing-away an Eclipse of the Full Moon occurs, and the other referring to modifications of the Athenian Triremes engineered before the final Naval Battle of Syracuse.

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